

USE OF UZBEK FOLK SONGS AND CLAPPING SAYINGS IN SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. This article shows the people's lifestyle, social and household life, work activities, views on nature and society, beliefs and religious ideas, feelings towards people and the world, artistic world, level of knowledge, happy and just times. expressed.

Keywords. Traditional, material, amateur, oral, theatrical, professional, live, diploma, gallows, wooden, spectacular, game, dance, puppet, social, folk.

Uzbek folk music - artistic, creative-practical and amateur activities of the public, folk oral art of traditional material and non-material culture, i.e. folklore, folk music, i.e. musical folklore, folk theater, including performing arts, folk games, i.e. dance, puppetry , gallows and wooden leg games, including folk circuses, are products of musical folklore.

The types of folk art, the creation and creative process of which is the participation of many people, are formed in accordance with the people's lifestyle, living conditions, level of social work, are passed from generation to generation, from teacher to student, are constantly perfected, polished, become more and more traditional, and finally, have the characteristics of professionalism, i.e. professionalism. has come down to us in live performance conditions and everyday practice.

People's lifestyle, social and domestic life, work activities, views on nature and society, beliefs and religious ideas, feelings towards people and the world, artistic world, level of knowledge, thoughts about a happy and just time are expressed in the examples of folk art. . Folk art has been developing since ancient times . With the development of society and the increasing division of labor, the specialization of some talented individuals in the genres of folk art has increased. In this way, entertainers, clowns, entertainers, puppeteers, dancers, entertainers, painters, potters, engravers, embroiderers, and folk art emerged, and lovers appeared. But in its creation and assimilation, the participation of the majority, each performance or practice, has been missing within the framework of long established traditions. Any art, creative activity, innovation took place within the framework of stable traditions and master-disciple relationships. On the one hand, the traditions themselves were developing, on the other hand, during each performance or practice, changes, innovations were introduced, and new copies of works were created. Some of them have been forgotten and have fallen out of practice.

Folk art plays an important role in the emergence and development of perfect art. On the other hand, perfect art also affects the development of national creativity and enriches it. The desire to preserve and develop examples of folk art in society, to restore lost ones, arose from the desire to satisfy one's elegant requirements, to live well, and to perfect one's life. Today, great opportunities and conditions have been created for the preservation and development of national creativity. This is confirmed by the functioning of state-level museums-reserves, the scientific study and publication of examples of folk art, the existence of many folklore-ethnographic ensembles, and the implementation of activities aimed at improving artistic amateurism.

The role and importance of song and music in the formation of personality has been shown in the scientific research works of musicologists with the help of many evidences. According to the sources, music education has a special place in

the development of a person's outlook, spirituality, morals, level of civilization, feelings.

The famous Russian composer D. B. Kabalevsky writes: "The great role of art and literature in moral education continues throughout a person's life." This in place Art school _____ subject , something textbook with irreplaceable " _____

this idea relied on h ahead to say maybe , boy identity meaning v iy-akhlo q iy doubt __ _ directly musi q a, his It 's a dead country _ _ _ _ _ the songs are performed in the background _ _ _ is increased . Spiritual - akh alq iy normal child _ _ _ _ _ absorb for , eng first of all , them morally and morally _ _ _ _ _ with introduction it is necessary . _ According to experts trust , spiritual and moral _ _ _ _ _ concepts The house q is divided into three groups h _ mu m kin :

1) spiritual and moral concepts _ _ _ _ _ statement to do _

2) spiritual - moral thought yuri t work ;

3) spiritual - moral _ conclusions let 's go _

Moral - akh l o q iy norms generosity , charity , goodness , respect , benevolence , responsibility , diligence _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ like of terms content knowing get it , follow it in your work to come means _

Russian writer N. A. _ Dobrolyubov's as written , k o' the majority people good and bad Get to work _ _ _ _ _ _ original the reason is because of them morals _ _ of norms mo h ability see _ imagination it 's because they couldn't do it .

Spiritual - akh l o qi y of concepts mo h ability see _ h is do sh for he or this in case of h all to him general work _ _ _ h am his result q is like that or that he found a day very careful _ with follow , thought conduct and his own personal conclusion What's up ? I need to take it . Deep learning of spiritual and moral standards in the educational process is desirable. Music education has great potential in this regard. Moral and moral standards gain stability only when they are tested many times, and as a real support of a person, they motivate his life behavior. It clearly shows how to act in which case.

The appeals, admonitions, and instructions contained in the thoughts and melodies given in the folk songs are the product of his life conclusions, which have been re-examined and polished as a result of the experience gained over the centuries. Every word spoken by the people is a "bullet" and it is natural that a person who does not read it will suffer in life. As a result of learning spiritual and moral concepts, comparing them to various events and psychological situations that occur in everyday life, well-formed habits, skills and abilities begin to form.

Music education plays a special role in children's ability to find their place in the class, school community, family, neighborhood during the period spent in general secondary education schools. Content-based music lessons, extracurricular activities, and a general musical environment are also important resources for developing children's spirituality.

The teacher's knowledge, talent, enthusiasm, advocacy, kindness, and advice are of leading importance in turning music lessons into a real educational tool.

The great power of music is that it can enter the inner world of a child and arouse his emotions. Psychologists say that music can penetrate into the largest, most delicate layer of neural networks in the hemispheres of the human brain, which cannot be affected by any other means. In these layers, huge reserves of human energy are stored, and good music can activate these mental energy and emotional reserves.

Psychologist I.A. Vartanyan explains why music has a special place among the blessings created by man for himself as follows: "...man created another sound language for himself, that is, music - emotion, feeling, mood, musical art."

The art of music has its own power, which is not present in any other subject or art. In this stockpile of "weapons" that can have a strong influence on a person, the unique professional characteristics of the art of music, in the "arsenal" of tools, are the sound timbre, that is, the color, the loudness of the sounds. lowness, variety of rhythm (method), harmony structures, variety of interval and

chord structure, dynamic tone, etc. are an incomparable means of influence that excites a person and creates miracles in the world of his feelings.

In the formation and development of a child's personality, the role of music, especially folk songs created from a series of people's heartaches, joys, sorrows, and hopes, is incomparable.

Folk songs are an art form that has been ingrained in the blood of the Uzbek people from generation to generation, and therefore a person who listens to folk melodies, laments and other national decorations cannot be indifferent to it. directly follows him, sings along, dances, that is, the music leads him into his magical world. Folk songs are not only a world of aesthetic appeal, but also a huge educational tool. Because at the core of human emotions lie spiritual and moral concepts, feelings, and conclusions.

In the words of the famous Russian pedagogue scientist V.A. Sukhomlinsky: "emotional-spirituality is the blood, body and heart of the profession, the firmness and strength of the soul, morality without emotion becomes a dry, lightless word that educates hypocrites."

In the process of mastering spiritual and moral qualities, new spiritual needs of children appear. Trying to satisfy these needs makes the child decide to strive and search for the goals and tasks he has set for himself. This movement is clearly visible in the child's childhood. To the opinions of pedagogic scientists. based on this, it can be said that the formation of children's spiritual and moral qualities by means of folk songs can be carried out in four main directions:

1. Motherland _ and people died _ _ _ It 's a good thing .
 2. Child labor , people and by them _ _ _ created died for blessings _ attitude forming , .
 3. Child 's society members i , q arinmates and him standing around _ He died to his peers relationship _
 4. His personal s as z ' z- in relation to himself q mixes q aror finds _
- Independence of the Uzbek people _ _ hand _ after entering , national-

meaning aviation - our system really _ _ _ _ _ to the owner rotation for wide opportunities was created . One of the main goals of education today is to instill in the young generation the spiritual wealth of our ancestors acquired over the centuries, to establish and regularly develop human qualities in them, to teach them to feel their duty and responsibility to the Motherland and the nation. Spiritual and moral qualities, such as children's love for the Motherland, work, and people, are of great importance in awakening spiritual needs and interest, and in educating spiritual activities and values. Also, spiritual and moral resources are a means of forming the components of spiritual virtue in a child.

Children's spiritual qualities consist of their intellectual, moral, political, economic, legal, environmental, aesthetic, artistic, religious culture and other multifaceted components. In the process of music education, parts of the composition of spiritual virtue are inculcated in the mind of the child in mutual unity and connection. Through folk songs, high moral qualities such as humanity, loyalty, contentment, love, justice, refinement, faith, positive attitude to work, distinguishing between religion and heresy, love for nature, understanding of duty and rights are formed in children.

If we look at the history of our country, in ancient times, our ancestors and mothers used national sports, active games and entertainment on holidays and outings. In particular, goat racing, wrestling on "Navroz holiday", "Harvest holidays", "Eid of Ramadan", "Eid of Sacrifice" and other holidays. Many different games and entertainments were held.

It is worth noting that, despite the long-lasting severe ideological pressure, the people of Uzbekistan as a whole managed to preserve their historical and cultural values and unique traditions that have been passed down from generation to generation. In particular, it is our duty to study the musical heritage of our musical culture and art created by our ancestors over the centuries. "Karsak" genre is of special importance in our folklore practice, along with genres such as alla, lapar, yalla, which have been preserved from the ancient past until today.

Applause is widely used and accompanied not only in Uzbek expressions, but also in musical expressions, performances and dance expressions that are the heritage of many other nations. Among them are theatrical "Maskharao'in" or "Horse game" and "Bear game" in the form of pantomime. They also have choruses, where the "choristers" accompany the player in the middle by clapping in various rhythmic patterns. In particular, it is our word that there are such games in Bulungur, Jomboy, Urgut districts of Samarkand region and that these games are still being performed during the Sayil and Navroz holidays. The game, of course, is led by applause. As the games gradually heat up, the performing clappers connect with each other through single claps, triple claps, five claps, seven claps, and even nine claps, taking on a rhythmically diverse character. Yallachi and laparists focus on the playful, satirical and humorous aspects of the verse that is sung to attract the attention of the audience. Expressions of the "Karsak" genre are almost the same as the yalla genre in terms of their performance.

Let's go. Beshkarsak karsak is a men's round game song. It is common among the Uzbek and Tajik peoples. It is especially popular in Samarkand , Bukhara, Surkhandarya, and Kashkadarya regions. A way of playing is created by clapping and squealing in the bass drum. According to some, the origin goes back to Zoroastrian rituals. The game and the term, which are performed alternately in the form of a series, consist of "one kars", "double kars", "five kars". In the recent past, the game of Beshkarsak lasted for hours at weddings and parties in rural areas. Currently, mainly folklore-ethno-graphic and amateur ensembles, for example, "Beshkarsak" ensemble from Urgut, are included in the program.

Some researchers include "Beshkarsak" or "Karsak Oyin" in the group of serial works, the small evidence of which is reflected in the naming of its components. For example: Five kars, three kars, double kars, one kars, seven kars and so on. Each of the claps has different content and performance characteristics. However, the number of claps they contain may not match the name of this genre. Nevertheless, the rhythmic basis of the five claps is consistent with the various

shouts in the poem. By means of these, specific rhythms are given to each component. The rhythmic structure of clapping , which is performed by many people along with the small "ha-ha-ha", is different in each part of the "Beshkarsak" series. In some cases, the last words that come after the words of the soloist are performed in unison by several singers without any notes at all . There are also types of performances in which he sings solo refrains, and the rest of the performers sing common refrains, for example, "chipra dalli-dalli", "yor-yor-yorone-e", "ho lallo" and so on.

In areas such as Samarkand-Bukhara, words like "oh guli bogiman biyo" are added to these general chants, and the next verses are sung again in Uzbek. This is a sign that these sayings are also spread among the Tajik peoples. "Beshkarsak" is usually performed by men, often young boys, and the style of performance observed in dance games also has characteristics related to the expression of certain emotions through masculine dance movements. In most cases, young men gather in a circle and clap their hands in some rhythmic way.

In Urgut District, a separate "Beshkarsak" ensemble performing clapping - was created , but currently clapping is performed mainly in folklore ethnographic ensembles and amateur circles. Examples of folk lore, created by the people for centuries and passed down from mouth to mouth, from generation to generation, have not lost their importance even today .

At this point, it should be mentioned that in recent years, the attention to Uzbek national music traditions has increased, and the processes of restoration of national values, customs and ceremonies are continuing. A number of important works aimed at learning, mastering, and further development of them are being carried out. It is not surprising that the contests that are being held on the scale of our republic will increase the positive influence of national genres among the people on the spirituality of young people. It is equivalent to ensuring the future of our music's longevity, perspective and development.

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